

Inguinal Bladder Hernia: A Rare Inguinal Hernia. Case Report

Jesús Alexis Martínez Rodríguez¹, Hector Abraham Peralta Ruiz², Leonel Lozano Lugo³

^{1,2,3}Department of General Surgery, High Specialty Medical Unit 71, IMSS Torreon Coahuila, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

-Inguinal bladder hernia is a rare clinical condition, accounting for 1–4% of all inguinal hernias, with a higher prevalence in older men. Its diagnosis is often incidental due to nonspecific symptoms, which can lead to intraoperative complications if not recognized in a timely manner.

Objective:

- To analyze the clinical characteristics, diagnostic methods, and therapeutic strategies for inguinal vesical hernia based on evidence published over the last decade.

Method:

- A review was conducted based on case reports, clinical series, and systematic reviews published between 2018 and 2024. Studies addressing the diagnosis, management, and outcomes of patients with inguinal bladder hernia were included.

Case Report:

- A 45-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department after being referred by his primary care provider for evaluation by general surgery due to a mass in the left inguinal region accompanied by pain and a decreased urine stream during urination.

Conclusion:

-Inguinal vesical hernia is an underdiagnosed condition that requires a high index of clinical suspicion. Computed tomography is the diagnostic tool of choice. Timely surgical management offers excellent results, minimizing complications.

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INTRODUCTION

A bladder inguinal hernia is a rare condition characterized by the protrusion of the urinary bladder through the inguinal canal, either partially or completely, into the hernial sac [1,2]. This condition accounts for less than five percent of all inguinal hernias and is most commonly observed in men over the age of fifty, particularly those with predisposing factors such as obesity, prostatic hypertrophy, abdominal wall weakness, and a history of previous surgeries [1,3,4,5]. The etiopathogenesis of inguinal bladder hernia is related to chronic increased intra-abdominal pressure and weakness of the connective tissue of the inguinal canal, which facilitates the displacement of the bladder into the hernial sac [1,2,6]. Pathophysiologically, bladder protrusion can cause partial obstruction of urinary flow, urinary retention, recurrent urinary tract infections, and, in rare cases, strangulation that compromises the organ's blood supply [4,7,9].

The clinical presentation is variable; patients are often asymptomatic or present with nonspecific symptoms such as a mass in the inguinal region, pain, or a sensation of

heaviness in the affected area. In some cases, Mery's sign may be observed, characterized by a decrease in urinary volume following compression of the hernia [11,3,5,7]. Large hernias or those associated with complications may present with urinary retention [9,10].

These hernias are classified based on the relationship between the bladder and the hernial sac: a complete hernia occurs when the entire bladder is within the sac, a partial hernia when only a portion is displaced, and a ureteral hernia when the ureter is involved [13,14]. Additionally, hernias are classified as direct, indirect, or scrotal based on the anatomy of the inguinal canal involved [12,14,15].

Diagnosis is typically made using imaging studies, with computed tomography being the most sensitive method for determining the extent of the hernia and bladder involvement [1,2,6,7,12,14]. Ultrasonography can be useful in the initial evaluation, while cystography provides precise information on bladder morphology and the extent of the hernial sac, making it particularly valuable in cases of symptomatic or large hernias [1,2,11,12]. Preoperative

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identification is crucial to avoid iatrogenic injury during surgical repair.

Treatment is primarily surgical, involving the reduction of the bladder into the abdomen and repair of the abdominal wall defect. Open techniques, such as the Lichtenstein repair, are the most commonly described, although laparoscopic approaches have gained popularity in recent years [8,14]. Within laparoscopic surgery, the transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) approach allows access to the inguinal region via abdominal insufflation and the placement of a prosthetic mesh between the peritoneum and the transversalis fascia. This approach is classified according to the location of the mesh and the technique used to close the peritoneum: TAPP with a flat mesh without fixation, TAPP with fixation using staples or sutures, and TAPP with complete peritoneal closure, each adapted to the complexity of the hernia and the surgeon's experience [14,15]. In cases of complicated hernias involving strangulation, bladder necrosis, or ureteral involvement, partial bladder resection or additional urological management may be necessary [9,13].

In summary, inguinal bladder hernia is a rare but significant condition due to the risk of urinary and surgical complications. Clinical suspicion, confirmation via imaging studies and cystography, and timely surgical repair—whether open or laparoscopic TAPP—are essential for successful management [1–15].

CLINICAL CASE

A 45-year-old male patient with a history of type 2 diabetes mellitus since 2009, long-standing systemic hypertension (no specific onset date reported), and an untreated inguinal hernia since 2007.

Current complaint: The patient presented to the emergency department with pain and swelling in the left inguinal region, accompanied by a decreased urine stream. He reported that the inguinal pain began 3 days ago, prompting him to visit his primary care provider, who subsequently referred him to this facility for evaluation by the general surgery department.

On targeted physical examination of the left inguinal region, a clear swelling is observed, with no apparent changes in color. On palpation, the patient reports intense pain, and when attempting to reduce the hernia, it cannot be reduced. An attempt was made to palpate the inguinal ring, but due to the presence of the mass, assessment was not possible.

It was decided to order preoperative laboratory tests, and due to the history of decreased urine stream during urination, a cystogram was performed to evaluate the urinary system for a probable inguinal-vesical hernia. (Figure 1,2,3). Following the study, two-thirds of the bladder was observed in the inguinal-scrotal region, leading to the decision for surgical intervention.

During the surgical procedure, a transverse incision was made in the left inguinal region, and the oblique aponeurosis

was identified, spermatic cord is dissected away from the surrounding structures; the hernial sac is opened to reveal bladder contents, which are dissected and reduced; the sac is closed and reduced; the joint area and inguinal ligament are dissected; an inguinal plasty is then performed using the Celdran technique; hemostasis is verified; and the incision is closed in layers, concluding the surgical procedure.

Figure 1: Negative cystogram

Figure 2: Cystogram showing a focus in the bladder

Figure 3: Complete cystogram

The surgical approach involves making a transverse incision in the left inguinal region, identifying the aponeurosis of the rectus abdominis muscle, opening it, and identifying the direct hernial sac. The sac is separated from the elements of

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the inguinal canal, opened to reveal vesicular contents, dissected, and reduced. The sac is closed, and the joint area and inguinal ligament are dissected. subsequently, inguinal plasty is performed using the Celdran technique, hemostasis is verified, and the incision is closed in layers, concluding the surgical procedure.

The findings revealed a Nyhus IIIB inguinal-scrotal hernia with a 20-cm hernial sac containing bladder contents.

In the postoperative period, the patient's course was uneventful, with no bleeding or complications in the scrotal region; therefore, it was decided to discharge the patient from the hospital.

Figure 4: Hernia Sac after dissection

Figure 5: Bladder as hernia sac content

DISCUSSION

A bladder hernia is a rare type of inguinal hernia, accounting for approximately 1 to 4 percent of cases. It is most common in older men and is frequently associated with predisposing factors such as obesity, lower urinary tract obstruction, and abdominal wall weakness (1,4,12). Despite its low incidence, its clinical significance lies in the possibility of it going unnoticed, since in many cases it is asymptomatic or presents with nonspecific symptoms, which delays diagnosis (2,3,5,12).

From a clinical standpoint, patients may present with an inguinal or inguino-scrotal mass accompanied by urinary symptoms such as dysuria, pollakiuria, or the characteristic

phenomenon of two-stage voiding, in which bladder emptying is completed by manual compression of the hernial region (11,5). However, a considerable proportion of cases are diagnosed incidentally during surgical procedures or imaging studies performed for other reasons (3,4,7,12). In critical settings, such as in patients hospitalized in intensive care units, diagnosis can be even more challenging due to the coexistence of multiple pathologies (2,12).

The bladder is involved in less than 4% of inguinal hernias, which means that diagnosis is difficult: less than 7% are diagnosed preoperatively and 16% postoperatively (12). However, preoperative diagnosis has improved significantly with the use of imaging studies, with computed tomography being the most sensitive method for identifying bladder contents within the hernial sac and determining their extent (1,4,12,14). Cystography is a valuable adjunct, as it allows direct visualization of the bladder morphology, its relationship to the hernial sac, and any associated diverticula or anomalies (11,12,14). Ultrasound can also be useful in the initial evaluation of patients with an inguinal mass or nonspecific urinary symptoms, provided certain diagnostic criteria are met: -A fluid-filled lesion within the scrotum that can be traced cranially to join the intra-abdominal portion of the bladder, -A pointed appearance of the cranial part of the scrotal mass, which enters the inguinal canal, - Changes in the lesion's volume and thickening of its wall following urination. Preoperative identification via imaging studies is essential for planning the procedure and preventing iatrogenic complications, such as bladder injury during hernia repair (4,7,12,14,15).

Another significant diagnostic test, known as intravenous urogram, has the advantage of ruling out other causes involving the upper urinary tract. Diagnostic signs known as the Reardon-Lowman triad have traditionally been described: - Lateral displacement of the lower third of one or both ureters, - A small, asymmetrical bladder, - Incomplete visualization of the bladder base.(15).

Regarding management, the treatment of choice is surgical, involving reduction of bladder contents and repair of the hernial defect. The Lichtenstein technique is widely used due to its low recurrence rate and consistent results (8,12). However, laparoscopic approaches, particularly transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) surgery, have proven to be of great importance in selected cases. This technique allows for a wide view of the inguinal region, precise identification of the hernial sac, and secure placement of the mesh between the peritoneum and the transversalis fascia, reducing the risk of bladder injury and improving postoperative recovery (14,15). TAPP surgery is classified according to the technique used for mesh placement and fixation: flat mesh without fixation, mesh fixed with staples or sutures, and complete peritoneal closure, allowing the approach to be adapted to the complexity of the hernia and the surgeon's experience. On the other hand, most inguinal bladder hernias are of the direct type and are divided into

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three subtypes: paraperitoneal, extraperitoneal and intraperitoneal (14,15). In special cases, such as massive, recurrent, or ischemically compromised bladder hernias, partial bladder resection or individualized surgical approaches may be necessary (6,10,12,13).

Associated complications include incarceration, strangulation, and, in rare cases, vascular compromise of the bladder, which can lead to necrosis if not treated promptly (9,12). Although these complications are uncommon, their presence significantly increases morbidity and mortality, highlighting the importance of early diagnosis through imaging studies and appropriate surgical management, whether open or laparoscopic TAPP (4,9,12,13,14).

The prognosis for patients with vesical inguinal hernias is generally favorable when timely surgical treatment is performed, with a low recurrence rate reported in the literature (1,8,12). However, the possibility of recurrence, especially in patients with persistent predisposing factors, underscores the need for adequate follow-up (10,12,13,15). Experience reported in case series and analyses of multiple patients highlights the importance of an individualized approach, preoperative planning based on imaging studies and cystography, and careful selection of the surgical technique, with TAPP laparoscopic surgery being a valuable tool in the modern management of these hernias (12–15).

Conclusion:

Overall, the available evidence on bladder inguinal hernias confirms that this is a rare but clinically significant condition, the diagnosis of which remains challenging. Based on the reviewed articles, it is observed that this condition predominantly affects elderly men with predisposing factors associated with increased intra-abdominal pressure or bladder emptying disorders. However, its clinical presentation is often nonspecific or even asymptomatic, which contributes to its underdiagnosis and to the fact that in many cases it is identified incidentally during surgery.

Studies agree on the importance of imaging tools, particularly computed tomography, as the most effective method for establishing a preoperative diagnosis and planning a safe surgical approach. Furthermore, it is emphasized that a high index of clinical suspicion is essential to avoid potentially serious complications, such as incarceration, strangulation, or iatrogenic bladder injury.

Regarding treatment, there is consensus that management is surgical, with reduction of the bladder contents and repair of the hernial defect being sufficient in most cases. Open techniques, such as the Lichtenstein repair, continue to be widely used, although the approach must be tailored to the patient's characteristics and the hernia complexity. On the other hand a bladder resection becomes an option only on exceptional cases.

Finally, the reviewed literature, consisting mainly of case reports and small series, highlights the need to continue generating higher-quality evidence. Nevertheless, current

findings suggest that timely diagnosis, supported by imaging studies, and appropriate surgical treatment are critical to achieving favorable outcomes and reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with this condition.

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